

Fatigue analysis of floating offshore wind turbines

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1 Introduction

As the world transitions towards sustainable energy, offshore wind energy is becoming increasingly critical. However, conventional fixed-bottom wind turbines face economic limitations in depths greater than 60 meters, rendering approximately 80% of global offshore wind resources inaccessible to them [1]. To overcome this challenge, floating offshore wind turbines (FOWTs) present a viable solution. These turbines can be deployed at much greater depths, allowing them to be placed farther offshore where winds are stronger and more consistent, and where they are not visible from the shoreline.

Despite currently accounting for only about 0.2% of total wind power worldwide [2], floating wind power is projected to grow to over 6% by 2030 [3]. This rapid expansion is driven by extensive research and development efforts, exemplified by projects like the TetraSpar [4]. However, while the (hydro-)dynamics of FOWT substructures are well-documented in literature, studies on the structural fatigue of these FOWTs are relatively scarce. Addressing this gap, the BEL-Float project [5], funded by the Energy Transition Fund of the Belgian federal government, aims to develop an open-source numerical method to assess fatigue loads, to evaluate the (local) accumulation of fatigue damage, and ultimately to predict the fatigue lifetime of the floater substructure with high accuracy. The OC4 DeepCWind FOWT [6], illustrated in Figure 1, is used as a reference to develop this method.

Figure 1: Illustration of the OC4 DeepCWind semi-submersible FOWT, as defined in [6]

2 Challenges and proposed methodology

Conducting a fatigue analysis of the substructure of a FOWT presents several challenges. In typical dynamic modeling approaches, such as those used in software packages like OpenFAST [7], a flexible tower is coupled with a rigid floater. However, this means that no internal forces and moments, and thus stresses can be extracted for the floater. As a result, most studies in literature that consider the fatigue of FOWT substructures focus solely on the fatigue at the tower base [8, 9], where forces and moments can easily be extracted from the dynamic analysis. On the other hand, only one research paper [10] exists to the authors knowledge that considers the fatigue of other critical locations, such as welded joints, of a FOWT substructure.

To perform a detailed fatigue analysis of these critical regions, knowledge of local stresses is required. This necessitates the development of a finite element (FE) model that considers the distributed pressure loads on the wetted surface due to waves and current acting on the structure, instead of the resultant forces at the centre of gravity (CoG), which are used in the rigid body analyses. To address this, a method is developed to accurately determine and implement the governing distributed hydrodynamic pressures onto a shell-based FE model, as illustrated on Figure 2. The method presented here is inspired by the works of Lee et al. [10] and Gao et al. [11].

First, a global (hydro-)dynamic time domain analysis is conducted using the open-source software OpenFAST. This analysis provides the following time domain outputs:

- the forces and moments at the transition piece between the tower and the floating platform;
- the forces at the mooring fairleads;
- the position and acceleration of the CoG of the floating platform in all six degrees of freedom (DOFs);
- the sea elevation at a reference point.

Figure 2: Schematic showing the method used to extract, calculate, and map the loads on an FE model

Next, a frequency domain simulation is conducted using Capytaine [12], an open source boundary element method (BEM) solver for linear potential flow, to determine complex pressure values across a range of frequencies. This is done at the centroid of all wetted elements in the FE mesh for Froude-Krylov, diffraction, and radiation loads. The reasoning behind selecting these locations will be explained later in this section. Since linear potential flow is being considered, the BEM solver disregards the cross braces. Their slender shape allows to assume that their contributions are negligible.

To transform the frequency domain pressures into useful time domain data, the following steps are performed for the diffraction problem, using the sea elevation $h(t)$ as input to the method:

1. it is assumed that the input $h(t)$ can be described as a finite Fourier series, i.e.:

$$h(t) = \Re \left[\sum_{n=1}^N h_n \exp(i(\omega_n t + \phi_n)) \right] \quad (1)$$

with N the number of frequencies, and h_n and ϕ_n respectively the amplitude and phase angle corresponding to the angular frequency ω_n .

2. a fast Fourier transform (FFT) is used to extract the amplitudes h_n , angular frequencies ω_n , and phase angles ϕ_n from $h(t)$;
3. since a linear problem is considered, the complex pressure values $p_{\text{diffraction}}(\omega)$ calculated in the BEM solver can be regarded as a transfer function;
4. the time domain diffraction pressure $p_{\text{diffraction}}(t)$ is then determined via:

$$p_{\text{diffraction}}(t) = \frac{1}{N} \Re \left[\sum_{n=1}^N h_n |p_{\text{diffraction}}(\omega_n)| \exp[i(\omega_n t + \phi_n + \angle p_{\text{diffraction}}(\omega_n))] \right] \quad (2)$$

where $|\cdot|$ denotes the absolute value and $\angle \cdot$ represents the phase angle.

The same method is used for the Froude-Krylov and radiation loads, using the sea elevation and the position of the CoG in all six DOFs, respectively, as input, and treating $p_{\text{Froude-Krylov}}(\omega)$ and $p_{\text{radiation}}(\omega)$, respectively, as transfer function.

As mentioned above, these time domain pressures are determined for the centroid of each wetted shell element of the FE mesh. This allows to directly assign each pressure component to their corresponding element, creating a distributed pressure field on the FE model. It is important to note that this method permits the use of different meshes for the BEM and FE analyses. Once the hydrodynamic loads have been applied, the accelerations of the CoG of the platform are used to calculate the inertial loads and are assigned to the model. Subsequently, the tower bottom loads, mooring loads, gravity loads, and hydrostatic pressure are applied. Finally, a quasi-static FE analysis is performed.

3 Progress and Future Work

The method described above is being developed in the context of the BEL-Float project. At this time, linear potential flow theory is considered, but the drag term of the Morison equation will additionally be implemented in the future. Afterwards, a multi-dimensional fatigue modelling strategy will be developed, as shown in Figure 3. From the shell element FE analysis of the substructure, fatigue critical welds will be identified and solid element submodels will be developed of the regions surrounding these welds. The hot spot stress approach [13] will be used to extract fatigue governing stress spectra, after which the rainflow counting method combined with the Palmgren-Miner damage rule will be employed to determine the local fatigue damage.

Figure 3: Schematic showing the multi-dimensional fatigue modelling strategy

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